

**PREVALENCE OF NECK PAIN AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH RISK
FACTORS DUE TO POOR ERGONOMICS AMONG PESHAWAR
DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY OFFICERS (PDA),
PAKISTAN: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: To determine the prevalence, risk factors, and impact of neck pain and related musculoskeletal disorders among office workers, with a specific focus on the role of ergonomics in prevention and management. The study also seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of ergonomic interventions and exercises in reducing the incidence and severity of neck pain and improving workplace productivity and quality of life.

METHODS: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Peshawar Development Authority (PDA) from July to October 2024. A total of 117 participants, aged 25 to 50 years, were included, with the sample size calculated using Raosoft at a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. Participants were selected using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. Data was collected using the Neck Disability Index and Rapid Office Strain Assessment questionnaires. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 27.0, employing descriptive statistics (graphs and tables) and the chi-square test for associations.

RESULTS: A total of 117 participants were assessed using the NDI and ROSA. NDI results showed 10 (8.5%) with mild disability, 44 (37.5%) moderate, 40 (34.2%) severe, 21 (17.9%) severe at the moment, and 2 (1.7%) with the worst disability. ROSA indicated 1 (0.8%) at no risk, 27 (23.1%) at low risk, and 89 (76.1%) at high risk. Of the participants, 112 were male and 5 female, with all females reporting moderate disability. Among males, NDI scores included 10 mild, 39 moderate, 40 severe, 21 severe at the moment, and 2 worst.

CONCLUSION: The study revealed that most participants were categorized as having moderate to severe disabilities, with only a small portion experiencing the most extreme level of disability. The majority of the participants were males, and all female participants were classified under moderate disability.

INTRODUCTION

Neck pain is described as discomfort or pain located in the cervical area, which may occur with or without radiating pain into one or both upper limbs. This condition is characterized by its duration of at least one day and can vary in intensity and nature it can significantly impact daily activities and quality of life (Dong et al., 2020). Neck pain is a prevalent condition that affects individuals of all ages and can significantly impact daily activities and quality of life. The causes of neck pain are diverse, and understanding the underlying mechanisms is crucial for effective management and treatment (Abdelsalam et al., 2023). Muscle strain is a frequent cause of neck pain. It usually happens due to overuse, bad posture for a long time, or sudden injuries. When the neck muscles are overused or kept in an uncomfortable position for too long, tiny tears can form in the muscle fibers (Direksunthorn et al., 2023). Neck pain can be classified into several categories based on various factors one key classification is based on the duration of symptoms, which can be acute (lasting less than six weeks) and sub-acute (lasting six weeks to three months) and, the pattern of pain can vary, with some individuals experiencing sharp, localized pain, while others may have a more generalized, dull ache or radiating pain into the shoulders and arms (Er et al.).

Adapting bodily, structural and cognitive ergonomics factors is crucial for reducing both physical and mental strain on workers by implementing ergonomics adjustments, such as optimizing work space design, ensuring proper posture, and providing suitable tools, organization can significantly minimize the risk of work related injuries affecting the cervical region (Alibsew et al., 2023).

Exercise can play a crucial role in managing neck pain (Lindblom & Österman, 2022). Gentle stretching exercises help improve flexibility in the neck muscles, reducing tension and discomfort (Mianehsaz et al., 2022). Targeted exercises for the cervical and upper back muscles enhance strength and support, which can relieve pain (Johnston et al., 2021). Engaging in aerobic exercises, such as walking or cycling, improves

circulation and overall physical fitness, benefiting neck health (Jindo et al., 2021). Learning to maintain proper alignment during daily activities can prevent strain on the neck and promote better posture. Incorporating these exercise based treatments can help relieve neck pain and improve overall well being (Suroso et al., 2024).

Ergonomics consists of the main components, this focuses on the body's anatomy and movement. It involves designing workspaces and tools to minimize physical strain and enhance comfort (Dong et al., 2020). This aspect looks at mental processes like workload, decision making, and the potential for human error (Karwowski & Zhang, 2021). It aims to create tasks that align with how people think and process information. This involves improving how work is structured, including communication, teamwork, and scheduling, to boost productivity and reduce stress (Tosi & Tosi, 2020).

METHODS:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Peshawar Development Authority (PDA) from July to October 2024. A total of 117 participants, aged 25 to 50 years, were included, with the sample size calculated using Raosoft at a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. Participants were selected using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. Data was collected using the Neck Disability Index and Rapid Office Strain Assessment questionnaires. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 27.0, employing descriptive statistics (graphs and tables) and the chi-square test for associations. Inclusion criteria follows the following points i-e Minimum 1 year experience, Didn't active in sports activities, Prolong working hours i.e more than 5hrs, Age 20-60 years. While exclusion criteria covers the following points i-e Done any medical procedure, Active lifestyle, Receiving any rehab treatment, Any muscular neck pain before job.

RESULTS

A total of 117 participants were assessed using the NDI and ROSA. NDI results showed 10

(8.5%) with mild disability, 44 (37.5%) moderate, 40 (34.2%) severe, 21 (17.9%) severe at the moment, and 2 (1.7%) with the worst disability. ROSA indicated 1 (0.8%) at no risk, 27 (23.1%) at low risk, and 89 (76.1%) at high risk. Of the participants, 112 were male and 5 female, with all females reporting moderate disability. Among males, NDI scores included 10 mild, 39

moderate, 40 severe, 21 severe at the moment, and 2 worst. In ROSA, 1 male was at no risk, 25 at low risk, and 86 at high risk; 2 females were at low risk and 3 at high risk. Age groups included 68 participants aged 25-35, 40 aged 35-45, and 9 aged 45-55, with varying risk levels across these groups. Overall, 1 was at no risk, 27 at low risk, and 89 at high risk.

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Mild Disability	10	8.5
	Moderate Disability	44	37.6
	Severe Disability	40	34.2
	Severe Disability at moment	21	17.9
	worst Disability	2	1.7
	Total	117	100.0

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	No Risk	1	0.8
	Low Risk	27	23.1
	High Risk	89	76.1
	Total	117	100.0

DISCUSSION

In this study, out of 117 participants, the NDI scoring showed that 10 (8.5%) had mild disability,

44 (37.5%), moderate disability, 40 (34.2%) ,severe disability, 21 (17.9%) had severe disability at the

moment, and 2 (1.7%) had the worst disability. ROSA scoring indicated that 1 (0.8%) was at no risk, 27 (23.1%) were at low risk, and 89 (76.1%) were at high risk. Out of 117 participants, 112 were male, and 5 were female. In NDI scoring for males: 10 had mild disability, 39 moderate, 40 severe, 21 severe at the moment, and 2 had the worst disability. All 5 females had moderate disability. For ROSA, among males, 1 was at no risk, 25 at low risk, and 86 at high risk, while 2 females were at low risk and 3 at high risk. terms of age groups, out of 117 participants, 68 were aged 25-35, 40 were 35-45, and 9 were 45-55. The NDI results showed varying levels of disability across these age groups. On ROSA, for the 25-35 age group, 1 participant was at no risk, 15 were at low risk, and 52 were at high risk. In the 35-45 age group, 8 were at low risk and 32 at high risk, while for 45-55, 4 were at low risk and 5 at high risk. Overall, 1 was at no risk, 27 at low risk, and 89 at high risk.

Goh, H. R., & Tan, K. L. carried out a study in 2024 in Bangladesh shows that office workers have a moderate higher prevalence rate of neck pain and it is 34.7%. the result of this study indicated that individual aged 40 years or above with neck holding the forward bend postoure for a prolonge time were higher chance to have neck pain(Hossain et al., 2024).the potential reason for this to support our study is both studies have moderate higher prevalence of neck pain in office workers which is 34.7% and 46.2%.

A 2021 study conducted in Iran by Derakhshanrad, N., Yekaninejad, M. S., Mehrdad, R., and Saberi, H., involved a large sample size of 1,602 participants. The participant provided a broad dataset, but it may differ in focus or methodology compared to smaller, more targeted studies(Derakhshanrad et al., 2021). The potential reason to didn't support our study is the large sample size used in the mentioned research study.

LIMITATION

1. It is only limited to single center (ie Peshawar development authority) that why the finding this study can't be generalize to general population.
2. This is a cross sectional study so there is not a strong evidence.

3. Due to lack of time and resources this study could not include a larger population

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that most participants were categorized as having moderate to severe disabilities, with only a small portion experiencing the most extreme level of disability. The majority of the participants were males, and all female participants were classified under moderate disability. Younger participants aged 25–35 showed higher disability levels compared to older age groups. On ROSA scoring, the findings showed that a significant proportion (76.1%) of participants were at high ergonomic risk, while very few had no risk at all. The risk levels were predominantly high across all genders and age groups. these results highlight the pressing need for workplace improvements, such as ergonomic adjustments, training on proper posture, and physical wellness programs. Additionally, the differences observed between genders and age groups emphasize the importance of tailored interventions to address specific needs.

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